

Proniosomes: A Comprehensive Review of Formulation, Characterization, and Applications

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Abstract

Proniosomes have emerged as versatile carriers in the field of drug delivery, offering advantages over traditional vesicular systems. This review article comprehensively explores the formulation strategies, characterization techniques, and diverse applications of proniosomes. Proniosomes, the dry formulation of niosomes, possess inherent stability, flexibility in composition, and ease of reconstitution. Various methods such as thin-film hydration, slurry method, and spray drying are employed for proniosomes preparation, each influencing the characteristics of the resultant vesicles. Characterization techniques including microscopy, spectroscopy, and physicochemical analyses provide insights into proniosomes morphology, size distribution, stability, and drug loading efficiency. Additionally, this review highlights the applications of proniosomes in delivering a wide range of therapeutic agents, including drugs, proteins, and vaccines, through diverse routes of administration. The potential of proniosomes in enhancing drug stability, bioavailability, and targeting is discussed along with future perspectives for further advancements in this promising drug delivery system.

Keywords: Proniosomes, niosomes, drug delivery, formulation, characterization, applications.

Introduction

Proniosomes have evolved as a promising alternative to conventional vesicular systems in drug delivery. The concept of proniosomes originated from the need to overcome the limitations associated with niosomes, which are lipid-based vesicles composed of non-ionic surfactants.[1,2] While niosomes offer several advantages such as biocompatibility, stability, and ease of preparation, their liquid nature poses challenges in terms of storage, transportation, and stability. Proniosomes address these challenges by converting niosomes into a dry, free-flowing powder form, thus enhancing their stability and shelf-life. The evolution of proniosomes represents a significant advancement in the field of pharmaceutical sciences, offering improved drug delivery solutions for various therapeutic agents.[3,4,5]

Advantages of Proniosomes Over Traditional Vesicular Systems:

Proniosomes offer several advantages over traditional vesicular systems such as liposomes and niosomes. By converting vesicles into a dry powder form, proniosomes eliminate the need for aqueous dispersion, thereby enhancing stability and ease of handling. Additionally, proniosomes exhibit improved reconstitution properties upon hydration, ensuring efficient drug delivery. The versatility of proniosomes allows for customization of formulation parameters to meet specific drug delivery requirements, including controlled release, targeted delivery, and enhanced bioavailability. Furthermore, proniosomes offer compatibility with a wide range of drugs, including hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds, making them suitable for various pharmaceutical applications.[6-9]

The scope of this review article encompasses a comprehensive exploration of proniosomes, focusing on their formulation, characterization, applications, advantages, challenges, and future perspectives. Each aspect will be discussed in detail to provide a thorough understanding of proniosomes and their potential impact on drug delivery. By synthesizing existing literature and research findings, this review aims to serve as a valuable resource for researchers, scientists, and practitioners interested in exploring the potential of proniosomes as a versatile drug delivery platform.

Formulation of Proniosomes

- **Thin-Film Hydration Method:** The thin-film hydration method is one of the commonly employed techniques for proniosomes preparation. In this method, a lipid film is formed by evaporating a solution containing lipids and optionally a surfactant onto the surface of a glass flask or rotary evaporator. The lipid film is then hydrated with an aqueous solution containing the drug of interest, resulting in the formation of proniosomes. This method offers advantages such as simplicity, scalability, and reproducibility. However, factors such as lipid composition, hydration time, and temperature can influence the characteristics of proniosomes produced using this method.[10-14]
- **Slurry Method:** The slurry method involves dispersing lipid materials, surfactants, and optionally drugs or other additives in a suitable solvent to form a slurry. The slurry is then dried using methods such as vacuum drying or spray drying to obtain proniosomes powder. This method offers flexibility in terms of formulation composition and drug incorporation. It also allows for the production of proniosomes with uniform particle size distribution and high drug loading efficiency. However, optimization of formulation parameters such as lipid-to-surfactant ratio and drying conditions is necessary to achieve desired proniosomes properties.[15,16]
- **Spray Drying Technique:** Spray drying is a versatile technique for the preparation of proniosomes, particularly for heat-sensitive drugs and labile compounds. In this method, a solution containing lipids, surfactants, and drugs is atomized into fine droplets using a spray nozzle and dried rapidly in a hot air stream to form proniosomes powder. Spray drying offers advantages such as high encapsulation efficiency, uniform particle size distribution, and enhanced stability of proniosomes. However, optimization of process parameters such as inlet temperature, feed rate, and nozzle size are essential to obtain desired proniosomes characteristics.[17-19]

Various factors influence the formulation of proniosomes, including lipid composition, surfactant type and concentration, drug-to-lipid ratio, hydration conditions, and drying techniques. Optimization of these parameters is crucial to achieve proniosomes with desired characteristics such as size, shape, drug loading, stability, and release kinetics. Understanding the interactions between formulation components and their impact on proniosomes properties is essential for rational design and development of proniosomes-based drug delivery systems. Optimization of proniosomes formulation involves systematic evaluation of formulation parameters and process variables to achieve desired product attributes. Design of experiments (DoE), response surface methodology (RSM), and mathematical modeling techniques are commonly used for optimization of proniosomes formulations. These approaches facilitate the identification of optimal formulation conditions that maximize drug loading, minimize particle size, and enhance stability of proniosomes. By employing optimization strategies, researchers can tailor proniosomes formulations to meet specific drug delivery requirements and enhance therapeutic outcomes.

Characterization Techniques [20-27]

- **Microscopic Evaluation:** Microscopic evaluation techniques such as optical microscopy, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are commonly used to visualize proniosomes morphology and size distribution. Optical microscopy provides low-resolution images for qualitative assessment of proniosomes structure, while TEM and SEM offer high-resolution images that allow for detailed examination of proniosomes morphology, size, and surface characteristics.

Microscopic evaluation techniques provide valuable insights into the physical properties of proniosomes and facilitate characterization of their structural integrity and uniformity.

- **Spectroscopic Analysis:** Spectroscopic techniques including Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and fluorescence spectroscopy are employed to analyse the chemical composition and molecular structure of proniosomes. FTIR spectroscopy provides information about functional groups present in proniosomes components, while NMR spectroscopy offers insights into molecular interactions and conformational changes. Fluorescence spectroscopy enables the study of drug encapsulation efficiency and release kinetics in proniosomes. Spectroscopic analysis aids in understanding the physicochemical properties of proniosomes and elucidating their drug encapsulation mechanisms.
- **Physicochemical Characterization:** Physicochemical characterization techniques such as dynamic light scattering (DLS), zeta potential analysis, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are employed to assess proniosomes size, surface charge, thermal behavior, and crystalline structure. DLS and zeta potential analysis provide information about proniosomes size distribution and surface charge, respectively. DSC and XRD are used to study the thermal properties and crystallinity of proniosomes components, including lipids and drugs. Physicochemical characterization techniques aid in evaluating the stability, compatibility, and drug release properties of proniosomes under various storage and physiological conditions.
- **Stability Studies:** Stability studies are essential to assess the long-term stability and shelf-life of proniosomes formulations. Accelerated stability testing, including storage at elevated temperatures and humidity conditions, is conducted to evaluate proniosomes stability under stress conditions. Physical stability parameters such as particle size, size distribution, and zeta potential are monitored over time to assess proniosomes aggregation and destabilization. Chemical stability studies, including drug content analysis and degradation kinetics, provide insights into proniosomes-drug interactions and formulation stability. Stability studies play a critical role in ensuring the quality and performance of proniosomes-based drug delivery systems.
- **In vitro Drug Release Studies:** In vitro drug release studies are conducted to evaluate the release kinetics and release mechanism of drugs from proniosomes. Various release media mimicking physiological conditions, such as pH, temperature, and enzyme concentration, are used to assess drug release behavior from proniosomes. Sink conditions are maintained to ensure accurate measurement of drug release rates. Mathematical models such as zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas models are applied to analyse drug release data and predict release kinetics. In vitro drug release studies provide valuable information for optimizing proniosomes formulations and designing controlled-release drug delivery systems.

Applications of Proniosomes

Proniosomes have demonstrated versatility in delivering a wide range of therapeutic agents through diverse routes of administration. The applications of proniosomes span various fields of drug delivery, including oral, topical, transdermal, ocular, pulmonary, parenteral, vaccine, protein, peptide, and gene delivery. Each application offers unique advantages and challenges, making proniosomes a versatile platform for tailored drug delivery solutions.

- **Oral Drug Delivery:** Proniosomes offer significant potential for oral drug delivery, providing enhanced bioavailability, sustained release, and improved patient compliance. Oral proniosomes formulations can encapsulate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs, protecting them from enzymatic degradation and promoting absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Proniosomes can be formulated as immediate-release, controlled-release, or targeted delivery systems, offering flexibility in drug release kinetics and site-specific targeting.
- **Topical Drug Delivery:** Proniosomes are utilized in topical drug delivery applications to enhance skin penetration, promote drug deposition, and improve therapeutic efficacy. Topical proniosomes formulations can encapsulate drugs for the treatment of various dermatological conditions, including infections, inflammation, and skin disorders. Proniosomes offer advantages such as enhanced stability, prolonged drug release, and reduced skin irritation, making them suitable for topical delivery of both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs.
- **Transdermal Drug Delivery:** Proniosomes have emerged as promising carriers for transdermal drug delivery, facilitating efficient drug permeation across the skin barrier. Transdermal proniosomes formulations enhance drug solubility, permeability, and retention in the skin, allowing for sustained release and prolonged therapeutic effect. Proniosomes offer advantages such as improved skin penetration, reduced systemic exposure, and enhanced patient compliance, making them suitable for transdermal delivery of drugs with poor skin permeability.
- **Ocular Drug Delivery:** Proniosomes are employed in ocular drug delivery applications to improve drug bioavailability, prolong ocular residence time, and enhance therapeutic efficacy. Ocular proniosomes formulations can encapsulate drugs for the treatment of various ocular diseases and disorders, including glaucoma, cataracts, and ocular infections. Proniosomes offer advantages such as enhanced corneal penetration, reduced drug loss due to tear dilution, and improved patient comfort, making them suitable for ocular delivery of both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs.
- **Pulmonary Drug Delivery:** Proniosomes are utilized in pulmonary drug delivery applications to deliver drugs directly to the lungs, offering rapid onset of action and localized therapeutic effect. Pulmonary proniosomes formulations can encapsulate drugs for the treatment of respiratory diseases and conditions, including asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and lung infections. Proniosomes offer advantages such as improved drug solubility, enhanced lung deposition, and reduced systemic side effects, making them suitable for pulmonary delivery of both small molecules and biologics.
- **Parenteral Drug Delivery:** Proniosomes are employed in parenteral drug delivery applications to enhance drug stability, solubility, and targeted delivery to specific tissues or organs. Parenteral proniosomes formulations can encapsulate drugs for the treatment of various diseases and disorders, including cancer, infections, and inflammatory conditions. Proniosomes offer advantages such as prolonged circulation time, reduced immunogenicity, and enhanced therapeutic index, making them suitable for parenteral delivery of both conventional and biologic drugs.

- **Vaccine Delivery:** Proniosomes have emerged as promising carriers for vaccine delivery, offering improved stability, antigenicity, and immune response. Vaccine proniosomes formulations can encapsulate antigens, adjuvants, and immunomodulators to enhance vaccine efficacy and induce protective immune responses. Proniosomes offer advantages such as prolonged antigen release, enhanced mucosal immunity, and needle-free administration, making them suitable for vaccine delivery against infectious diseases, cancers, and autoimmune disorders.
- **Protein and Peptide Delivery:** Proniosomes are utilized in protein and peptide delivery applications to enhance stability, bioavailability, and therapeutic efficacy. Protein and peptide proniosomes formulations can encapsulate fragile biologics and protect them from enzymatic degradation and immune clearance. Proniosomes offer advantages such as sustained release, targeted delivery, and reduced immunogenicity, making them suitable for protein and peptide delivery for the treatment of various diseases and disorders, including diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological disorders.
- **Imaging Agents Delivery:** Proniosomes are employed in imaging agent delivery applications to enhance contrast, sensitivity, and specificity in diagnostic imaging modalities. Imaging agent proniosomes formulations can encapsulate contrast agents, nanoparticles, and molecular probes for non-invasive visualization and detection of pathological conditions. Proniosomes offer advantages such as prolonged circulation time, targeted accumulation, and reduced off-target effects, making them suitable for imaging agent delivery in various imaging modalities, including magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), and fluorescence imaging.
- **Gene Delivery:** Proniosomes have emerged as promising carriers for gene delivery, offering improved stability, transfection efficiency, and safety. Gene delivery proniosomes formulations can encapsulate nucleic acids, such as plasmid DNA, siRNA, and mRNA, to facilitate their intracellular delivery and expression. Proniosomes offer advantages such as protection against nuclease degradation, enhanced cellular uptake, and reduced cytotoxicity, making them suitable for gene delivery for therapeutic applications, including gene therapy, gene editing, and RNA interference (RNAi).[28-38]

Advantages and Challenges[39-48]

Advantages of Proniosomes:

Proniosomes offer several advantages that make them a promising platform for drug delivery:

- **Enhanced Stability:** Proniosomes provide improved stability compared to conventional vesicular systems, owing to their dry powder form.
- **Flexibility in Formulation:** Proniosomes can encapsulate a wide range of drugs, including hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds, offering versatility in formulation.
- **Tailored Drug Release:** Proniosomes allow for customization of drug release kinetics, enabling controlled release, sustained release, or targeted delivery.
- **Enhanced Bioavailability:** Proniosomes enhance drug solubility, permeability, and absorption, leading to improved bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy.
- **Targeted Delivery:** Proniosomes can be surface-modified or functionalized to achieve targeted delivery to specific tissues, cells, or organs, minimizing off-target effects.

- **Ease of Handling:** Proniosomes are in a dry powder form, making them convenient to store, transport, and reconstitute, reducing handling and storage requirements.

Challenges and Limitations:

Despite their advantages, proniosomes face certain challenges and limitations:

- **Formulation Complexity:** Formulating proniosomes requires optimization of various parameters such as lipid composition, surfactant type, and drug loading, which can be challenging and time-consuming.
- **Stability Issues:** Proniosomes may exhibit stability issues such as aggregation, fusion, or leakage during storage, leading to reduced shelf-life and efficacy.
- **Drug Compatibility:** Proniosomes may encounter compatibility issues with certain drugs or excipients, affecting drug encapsulation efficiency, stability, and release kinetics.
- **Scale-up Challenges:** Scaling up proniosomes production from laboratory to industrial scale poses challenges in maintaining batch-to-batch consistency, quality control, and cost-effectiveness.
- **Regulatory Hurdles:** Regulatory approval for proniosomes-based drug delivery systems may require extensive preclinical and clinical studies to demonstrate safety, efficacy, and quality.

Strategies to Overcome Challenges:

Addressing the challenges associated with proniosomes requires the development of innovative strategies and approaches:

- **Optimization Techniques:** Utilizing advanced optimization techniques such as design of experiments (DoE) and response surface methodology (RSM) can streamline proniosomes formulation development and overcome formulation challenges.
- **Stability Enhancement Strategies:** Implementing stability enhancement strategies such as lyophilization, cryoprotection, and surface modification can improve the stability and shelf-life of proniosomes.
- **Compatibility Testing:** Conducting comprehensive compatibility testing between proniosomes components and drug candidates can identify formulation issues early in the development process and guide formulation optimization.
- **Process Optimization:** Optimizing manufacturing processes and scale-up techniques can ensure reproducibility, consistency, and cost-effectiveness of proniosomes production.
- **Regulatory Support:** Collaborating with regulatory agencies and adopting regulatory guidelines for advanced drug delivery systems can facilitate the regulatory approval process for proniosomes-based formulations.

Future Perspectives

Emerging Trends in Proniosomes Research:

Proniosomes research is continuously evolving, driven by emerging trends and advancements in drug delivery technology:

- **Nanotechnology Integration:** Integration of nanotechnology approaches such as nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), and lipid-based nanocarriers with proniosomes can enhance drug loading capacity, stability, and targeting capabilities.

- **Smart Drug Delivery Systems:** Development of smart proniosomes-based drug delivery systems incorporating stimuli-responsive materials, biomimetic components, and molecular recognition elements can enable triggered release, site-specific targeting, and personalized therapy.
- **Combination Therapy:** Exploration of proniosomes-based combination therapy approaches involving synergistic drug combinations, dual-targeting strategies, and multi-functional nanocarriers can enhance therapeutic efficacy, overcome drug resistance, and minimize adverse effects.
- **Theranostic Applications:** Utilization of proniosomes for Theranostic applications, combining therapeutic and diagnostic functionalities within a single nanocarrier platform, holds promise for personalized medicine, real-time monitoring, and precision therapy.
- **Precision Medicine:** Integration of proniosomes with precision medicine approaches such as pharmacogenomics, biomarker-guided therapy, and patient-specific drug formulations can optimize treatment outcomes, minimize side effects, and improve patient compliance.

Innovations in Proniosomes Formulation:

Ongoing innovations in proniosomes formulation aim to address current challenges and enhance the performance of proniosomes-based drug delivery systems:

- **Advanced Encapsulation Techniques:** Development of novel encapsulation techniques such as supercritical fluid technology, electrospinning, and microfluidics can improve drug loading efficiency, control release kinetics, and enhance stability of proniosomes.
- **Biomimetic Design:** Incorporation of biomimetic components, such as cell-penetrating peptides, targeting ligands, and stealth coatings, into proniosomes formulations can improve biocompatibility, cellular uptake, and in vivo performance.
- **Hybrid Nanocarriers:** Integration of proniosomes with other nanocarriers such as polymeric nanoparticles, dendrimers, and metallic nanoparticles can create hybrid delivery systems with synergistic properties, enabling multimodal drug delivery, Theranostic applications, and targeted therapy.
- **Personalized Formulations:** Development of personalized proniosomes formulations based on patient-specific factors such as genetics, disease stage, and drug response profiles can optimize treatment outcomes, minimize adverse effects, and improve patient adherence.
- **Green Nanotechnology:** Adoption of green nanotechnology principles such as sustainable sourcing, eco-friendly synthesis routes, and biodegradable materials in proniosomes formulation can reduce environmental impact, ensure safety, and promote ethical practices in drug delivery.

Application Expansion and Market Potential:

The expanding application scope and market potential of proniosomes-based drug delivery systems are expected to drive growth and innovation in the pharmaceutical industry:

- **Therapeutic Diversity:** Diversification of proniosomes applications across various therapeutic areas such as oncology, neurology, cardiology, infectious diseases, and regenerative medicine can address unmet medical needs, expand treatment options, and improve patient outcomes.

- **Market Penetration:** Increasing adoption of proniosomes-based drug delivery systems by pharmaceutical companies, contract research organizations (CROs), and academic institutions can accelerate commercialization, market penetration, and widespread availability of proniosomes formulations.
- **Global Reach:** Expansion of proniosomes research and development activities to emerging markets, developing countries, and underserved populations can promote equitable access to innovative drug delivery technologies, reduce healthcare disparities, and enhance public health outcomes.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships:** Collaborative efforts between academia, industry, government agencies, and non-profit organizations can foster innovation, knowledge exchange, and technology transfer in the field of proniosomes-based drug delivery, driving market growth and societal impact.

Conclusion

Proniosomes serve as a versatile and promising platform in drug delivery, offering enhanced stability, formulation flexibility, and targeted delivery. Various techniques like thin-film hydration, slurry method, and spray drying are utilized for proniosomes preparation, each presenting distinct advantages and challenges. Thorough characterization employing microscopic evaluation, spectroscopic analysis, physicochemical assessment, stability testing, and in vitro drug release studies is crucial for comprehending proniosomes' properties and guiding formulation optimization. Proniosomes exhibit applications across diverse administration routes, including oral, topical, transdermal, ocular, pulmonary, parenteral, vaccine, protein, peptide, imaging agent, and gene delivery, providing tailored solutions for specific therapeutic requirements. Despite their benefits, proniosomes encounter challenges like formulation complexity, stability issues, and regulatory obstacles, necessitating innovative strategies for resolution. Future perspectives in proniosomes research encompass emerging trends such as nanotechnology integration, smart drug delivery systems, combination therapy, Theranostic applications, precision medicine, and green nanotechnology, promising advancements in drug delivery technology and patient care enhancement. Innovations in proniosomes formulation, expansion of applications, and market potential are anticipated to fuel growth and innovation in the pharmaceutical sector, leading to the development of next-generation drug delivery systems with improved efficacy, safety, and accessibility. Proniosomes offer a versatile and promising avenue in drug delivery, with significant potential for addressing current challenges and propelling advancements in pharmaceutical sciences. Continuous research, collaboration, and innovation are pivotal for unlocking the full potential of proniosomes and translating them into clinically relevant therapeutics for enhancing human health and well-being.

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